

THE PEDAGOGICAL NEED FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATIONAL AND COMBAT QUALITIES IN THE FUTURE MILITARY LEADERS OF PRELIMINARY TRAINING BEFORE THE CALL

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Abstract. *This article discusses the implementation of educational standards and principles in military training based on a competence-based approach. The main ideas, principles and methods of the competence approach in relation to military training are described. The basic concepts of competence and the classification of competencies in the context of the military educational system are considered. The problems and prospects of implementing the competence approach in military training are analyzed.*

Keywords: *military training, cadet, competence approach, skills, basic competence, competence, difficult situation, practical training, specialty.*

Introduction. In the modern conditions of peace and military activity, the military leaders of initial pre-conscription training play a special role. They are a key link in the training of conscripts for military service and are important in ensuring combat readiness and the effectiveness of military service. One of the main tasks of the military leaders of initial pre-conscription training is the formation and development of educational-combat qualities in student-youth. Training-combat qualities are an integral part of military service and are a complex set of skills, qualifications and qualities necessary for the effective performance of military tasks. They include physical fitness, tactical training, teamwork and leadership skills, stress resistance, moral and psychological stability, among others. The pedagogical development of educational and combat qualities in the future military leaders of preliminary training before the call-up has its own characteristics and requires a special approach. The process of developing these qualities should be systematic, focused and based on the principles of pedagogical science. It should include theoretical understanding of concepts and principles, as well as the practical development of skills and competencies through training. However, the existing practice of the formation and development of training-combat qualities among future military leaders of initial pre-draft training has its drawbacks. Often in the educational process, insufficient attention is paid to the development of educational-combat qualities and skills, as a result of which graduates have difficulties in putting into practice the knowledge and skills acquired during the study process.

If we look at history, then the Great Commander Amir Temur made a significant contribution to the improvement of training and combat qualities in the fighters of his time. Amir Temur's military concept was based on strict discipline, high physical fitness and practical use of tactics, strategy. In particular, Amir Temur was a major contributor to the improvement of training and combat qualities in the fighters of his time. His selection strategy, various types of training, development of tactical and strategic techniques, and physical fitness helped him create a strong and disciplined military force that achieved great victories on the battlefield.

In addition, Grand Commander Jaloliddin Manguberdi made a significant contribution to improving training and combat qualities in the fighters of his time. He was noted for his fighting skills, leadership skills, and strategic thinking. His extensive training, including physical and psychological training, training, and training in combat skills, and the use of modern tactics, has made his Army effective and successful in the war effort.

On the development of training and combat qualities in military training cadets, the American general and politician George Marshall commented, namely, “in order to succeed in military education, cadets need to develop not only their physical skills, but also the ability to work in a team, make decisions in stressful situations and concentrate even in the most extreme conditions.”

Also, Israeli historian and military theorist Martin Van Creveld commented, “The Academic-combat qualities play an important role in the formation of the character of the cadet and his readiness to carry out military tasks. These qualities include discipline, perseverance, stress resistance and the ability to adapt to changing conditions and make decisions quickly”.

According to Swedish military theorist Henrik Samuelsson, “the development of training-combat qualities in military training cadets is an integral part of their professional growth. With only a high level of physical and mental training, young military personnel can effectively fulfill their duties and ensure the safety of their country,” the statement commented.

David Goldfein, former commander-in-chief of the U.S. Air Force, commented, “training-combat qualities such as leadership, strategic thinking, and training ability are important factors for a military career. In order for cadets to become effective leaders and professionals in their field of activity, it is necessary to develop these qualities.”

From the above points, we can note that in the process of forming the character of a cadet of military education and his readiness to perform military tasks, educational and combat qualities play an important role. These qualities shape discipline, perseverance, stress resistance and ability to adapt to changing conditions and make decisions quickly in cadets. Pre-conscription initial training provides the basis for the development of such qualities in future military leaders and competencies in military activities.

Training-combat qualities include the performance of training tasks and the improvement of the skills necessary for effective work in the military environment. The main goal of the development of training and combat qualities is to create a strong and effective military personnel and institution that can successfully fulfill its tasks and provide security.

Having considered the scientific literature, we can say that such qualities of the future military leader of initial pre-conscription training include purposefulness, intensity, perseverance and courage, perseverance and endurance, discipline and self-government, and others on this basis, the opportunities in the field of military education increase, and at the same time their educational and combat qualities form.

Purposefulness - the cadet has clearly defined goals and direction of development. He understands the importance of studying and seeks to achieve high results. Such a cadet does not waste time and always focuses on self-development and improving knowledge and skills. Purposefulness in the development of the student's educational activities has several aspects. Purposefulness is an integral part of the training and combat qualities of a cadet, since it controls his actions and helps to achieve success in training activities.

Intensity is one of the important training-combat qualities of a cadet that contributes to the effective development of training activities, and it has the ability to overcome obstacles in the course not to give up difficulties with intensity and to achieve training goals. He is not discouraged when he fails, but finds the strength and motivation to continue the work and succeed. Thus, intensity is an indispensable quality of the cadet and contributes to its successful development in educational activities. It helps to overcome difficulties, achieve goals and effectively use potentiality.

Persistence is an important training-combat quality that contributes to the development of the cadet's training activities, which implies the ability to make decisions of determination and act on the basis of trust and accuracy. A cadet with this quality will not get lost in the face of complex tasks or problems, but will look for solutions and take the necessary measures to solve them. In general, rigor is an important quality that helps the cadet to develop effectively in educational activities. He gives her the strength and confidence to overcome obstacles and achieve her goals.

Courage is one of the important training and combat qualities of a cadet that helps to develop training activities, which means that the cadet is ready to take responsibility and take risks in order to achieve his educational goals. He is not afraid to go beyond his comfort zone and try new approaches and learning methods. In general, courage is an important quality that helps the cadet to develop effectively in educational activities. She gives him the strength and confidence to overcome difficulties, failures and achieve his goals.

Perseverance is one of the main training and combat qualities of a cadet, which contributes to the development of his educational activities. Perseverance refers to the ability of the cadet to maintain motivation and continue to work on achieving training goals even in the context of difficulties and obstacles. Perseverance the cadet does not retreat with failures or a decrease in motivation, but finds strength and constantly continues his educational activities. Thus, perseverance is an indispensable quality of the cadet and contributes to its successful development in educational activities. This allows you to overcome difficulties, maintain high motivation and effectively use your resources to achieve your goals.

Endurance is one of the essential qualities for the development of the cadet's training and combat activities, which includes the ability to focus and focus on a task or goal, despite the difficulties or distractions that arise. The endurance cadet does not lose focus and does not succumb to stress or pressure, which allows him to learn effectively even in difficult conditions or difficult situations. By developing endurance, the cadet receives not only stress resistance, but also the ability to self-organize and educate himself. He is independent and responsible and determines how to plan his time and work in a targeted mode to achieve training goals. This quality of endurance has a great influence on the development of the cadet's educational activities, helping him to be successful and effective in his educational endeavors.

Discipline is one of the qualities that plays an important role in the development of the cadet's training and combat activities, and the cadet involves self-control and self-discipline. A disciplined cadet seeks to control his actions and decisions, take responsibility for his actions and not violate the established rules.

Self-control is one of the most important training-combat qualities that plays a decisive role in the development of the cadet's educational activities. Self-control includes the ability to control and regulate behavior, emotions, thoughts, and behaviors in the academic field. A restrained and controlling cadet knows how to behave without succumbing to emotional outbursts,

distractions or temptations. It can focus on learning material and tasks, while avoiding spraying attention.

Dignity is one of the most important educational-combat qualities that plays an important role in the development of the cadet's educational activities. Dignity refers to the ability of the cadet to respect himself to those around him, to strive for moral behavior and to act in accordance with the principles of morality. A cadet with dignity resists temptations or negative influences, has dignity and self-esteem in any situation.

Independence is one of the most important educational and combat qualities that plays a decisive role in the development of the cadet's educational activities. Independence refers to the ability of a cadet to think, make decisions and act independently without external dependence or manipulation. A cadet with independence knows how to analyze information, identify the strengths and weaknesses of his decisions, convey his point of view and act in accordance with it.

Immersion is one of the most important educational-combat qualities that significantly affect the development of the cadet's educational activities. Hacked symbolizes the ability of the cadet to overcome his fears and doubts, to show determination and strength in difficult situations. The butterfly cadet is ready to overcome obstacles, despite the possible risks or difficulties that may arise. Even if those around him can doubt or worry, he is able to act.

Initiative is one of the main educational and combat qualities of a cadet that has a significant impact on the development of educational activities, which implies the ability of a cadet to be active, propose new ideas, make decisions and take initiative in educational work and service activities. An enterprising cadet does not expect instructions from others, but independently develops plans for actions and carries them out. He is ready to propose new approaches and ideas, independently solve problems and exceed expectations.

All the qualities mentioned above play an important role in the development of the training activities of cadets and help them become more effective and qualified military personnel. In the process of studying special literature, a number of terms and concepts can be found that form the basis for the development of educational-combat qualities. These include:

Physical fitness is regular exercise that includes exercise, running, pulling, and other exercises aimed at developing endurance. Physical fitness helps cadets overcome physical difficulties and get used to training, which in turn helps to develop courage, hasty, discipline, perseverance, endurance and perseverance.

Psychological (mental) training is training in stress management techniques, training in developing confidence, motivation and concentration in stressful situations. Cadets learn to understand their feelings, control them and be persistent and calm in difficult, dangerous situations.

Tactical and strategic training – training (combat) training and simulations aimed at developing tactical, strategy and military operations management skills. Cadets learn tactical principles aimed at success and effective solution of problems in combat situations.

Team cooperation – collective training, including the performance of training-combat tasks in the team. During such training, cadets learn to work in a team, develop communication skills, establish and support cooperation and coordination with the team.

Moral training – the formation of high moral values and understanding and respect the rules and laws of military ethics during training and combat operations. Cadets learn to be honest, responsible and serve the highest interests of their country and community.

All these elements together form the basis for the development of training and combat qualities in military training. They combine physical, tactical, psychological and moral training, as a result of which they help cadets become qualified and successful military specialists.

The initial preparation of the military training of future military leaders before the call, self-control with freedom is an important aspect of the development of their initial training and combat qualities. This condition is the initial period and requires taking into account the interests and abilities of the cadet, as well as his level of motivation. In this regard, self-control with freedom plays a special role, since it allows the cadet to actively control and adjust his behavior and thinking in accordance with the tasks and requirements of military training. For this reason, prospective military leaders develop important qualities such as self-discipline, responsibility, punctuality, emotion management, and decision-making ability in stressful situations. They will also have the opportunity to consciously focus on achieving goals and gradually improve their military professional skills. Thus, self-government with freedom plays an important role in creating a solid foundation for future military leaders, ensures their effective adaptation to the requirements of military service and contributes to their successful professional development. Self-management with freedom is a topic that attracts the attention of scientists and researchers in the field of mental and physical development of cadets. Many researchers have expressed their opinion on the importance of this aspect at the initial stage of military training and its impact on the development of primary training and combat qualities.

For example, Mikhail Rostovsky, professor at the Russian Institute for Strategic Studies, argues that self-government with freedom is the basis for the formation of basic professional skills in future military leaders. He argues that the ability of cadets to control their thoughts, feelings and actions plays a decisive role in achieving goals and making decisions under the stress and uncertainty of combat situations.

Dr. Linar Islamov, a psychologist and researcher at the Institute of psychological research, also emphasizes the importance of free self-government in future military leaders. He argues that this ability allows them to develop motivation, concentrate and control their emotions, which is considered necessary skills in a military context.

These scholars and many others recognize that libertarian self-government plays an important role in developing the basic training-combat qualities of future military leaders. They note that training this skill at the initial stage of training is a guarantee of the formation of the professional skills of military leaders and their successful military service.

For the successful professional training of future military leaders in preliminary training before the call-up, it is necessary to actively develop their training and combat qualities. To this end, the following tasks are set: to maximize the interest of coursans in initial preparation until the call; to attract additional external resources to improve this preparation; to expand educational opportunities during initial preparation until the call.

According to cadets, it is an important process for them to develop such qualities as Independence, perseverance, perseverance, courage, initiative, intensity, dignity, superstition, endurance, discipline. As individuals, they are interested in self-development of educational-combat qualities and, responding to the needs of development, have the opportunity to do it independently. It is noted that it is necessary not to start the process, but to organize specific and targeted work on the development of these qualities in cadets.

The pre-conscription primary preparatory training lesson plays an important role in the development of the training and combat qualities of cadets and is the main form of military training. The difference from other forms of the lesson is that the lesson has advantages, since it is organized, systematic and mandatory. It is based on a scientific program and is designed for long service life. The class is conducted under the guidance of a pre-conscription specialist (by a military officer).

Test results on the qualities of initiative and perseverance showed their special manifestation, which is not associated with other features of training and combat qualities. Cadets, based on their capabilities, sought to achieve positive results in various areas of activity using these qualities. Initiative, in turn, is a positive character trait that manifests itself in the ability to make independent and active actions. Persistence also occupies a special place among the educational-combat qualities, which are considered as an independent component when interacting with them relatively slowly.

In the daily active activities of cadets, educational and combat qualities play a special role. For example, completing assignments in a particular activity or educational process requires perseverance from the cadet. In order to form this quality in the cadet, it is important to develop such educational and combat qualities as courage, perseverance and reliability. Success in any activity, including study, depends on the level of endurance of the cadet. Endurance is the most valuable character trait that manifests itself in the ability to achieve set goals, despite difficulties and obstacles. Some cadets show perseverance in all areas of activity, for others this quality is manifested only in some areas associated with their interests. The results showed that the quality of perseverance is highly correlated with training-combat qualities such as courage, independence and endurance.

The level of perseverance of Cadets is determined by their confidence in the ability to achieve the goal, motivation, attitude to the development of training-combat qualities to overcome difficulties. However, the manifestation of perseverance depends to some extent on the nature of the nervous system.

The attentiveness of the future military leaders of preliminary training before the call-up is interconnected with various training and combat qualities. The mindfulness attitude is moderately related to purposefulness. This is because, in order to achieve the goal, the cadet must be attentive and thorough in completing each task. Therefore, it is important in cadets to form a sense of responsibility for their actions and bring what they started to the end.

It is clear that the degree of purposefulness depends on responsibility, and the higher the responsibility, the higher the purposefulness. Also, perseverance depends to some extent on such qualities as endurance and caution. The persistence of future military leaders largely depends on the level of responsibility, that is, on the timely and correct performance of their duties. This situation is explained by the fact that the necessary level of activity is maintained in the performance of the task, which is determined by the level of responsibility during the activity. Therefore, the cadet must show high endurance when overcoming difficulties and obstacles that arise in the process of achieving the goal. It should also closely monitor changes in its activities and training and service activities.

Pre-conscription initial training there is a correlation between the basic training-combat qualities that support and develop each other during the process of activity of future military leaders. Some training-combat qualities that can be considered as separate elements are also one

of the many characteristics of personality. Also, some educational and combat qualities that manifest as an independent component can be embodied in the form of a characteristic feature from many features of the personality character.

Based on the feasibility of the above and subsequent work on the development of a system of requirements for the education of future military leaders, taking into account the psychological and psychophysiological characteristics that arise during this period, and taking into account all aspects, the following recommendations for the development of training and combat qualities can be made:

formation and development of a sense of responsibility for personal behavior in future military leaders of preliminary preparation before the call;

preliminary preparation before the call-up is to give future military leaders a set of various complex and risk-related tasks, as well as to control their execution and outcome;

preliminary preparation before the call to conduct training and training sessions on the formation of combat qualities with future military leaders. Pre-conscription initial training there is a correlation between the basic training-combat qualities that support and develop each other during the process of activity of future military leaders. Some training-combat qualities that can be considered as separate elements are also one of the many characteristics of personality. Also, some educational and combat qualities that manifest as an independent component can be embodied in the form of a characteristic feature from many features of the personality character.

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CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the introduction of educational standards and principles on the basis of a competency approach to military education is a necessary and urgent step for the development of cadets and their preparation for the service of the Armed Forces. A competency approach allows you to focus not only on knowledge, but also on the development of skills, qualifications and personal qualities necessary for successful military service. The implementation of a competency approach also helps to more deeply and firmly master the material and form stable skills that will be useful for graduates of military education during their service activities. Cadets will have the opportunity to actively participate in practical projects, put their knowledge into practice and develop their social and professional competencies. However, it is necessary to take into account such features of military education as strict execution of instructions, subordination and discipline. Therefore, the introduction of a competency-based approach should be adapted to the specifics of the military sphere.

In general, the introduction of a competency approach to military education provides opportunities for individual development, the development of leadership qualities and the training of a future military specialist. It helps to improve the quality and efficiency of training military specialists, which is an important factor for the security and protection of the country.

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